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Beyond Ken and Barbie: Uncovering the Coming-Out Stories of Adolescent Lesbians

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Abstract

Despite the Philippines' apparent acceptance of the LGBTQ+ community, adolescent lesbians continue to face significant challenges, particularly during the coming out process. This study explores the intersection of cultural norms and religious beliefs in the Philippines and how these factors influence the decisions of adolescent lesbians to disclose their sexual identity. Employing semi-structured interviews and purposive sampling, the researchers gathered personal narratives from seven participants residing in the City of Mandaluyong. The data, analyzed through thematic coding, revealed a spectrum of experiences. While some participants described positive coming out experiences, characterized by familial acceptance and support from LGBTQ+ communities, others encountered considerable obstacles, including societal stigmas and restrictive familial expectations. The study underscores that the coming out journey remains fraught with difficulties, despite evolving societal attitudes. However, it also highlights the resilience of adolescent lesbians, who, despite the challenges, find strength and positive outcomes in their experiences. This research contributes to a deeper understanding of the complexities surrounding the coming out process in the Philippine context, emphasizing both the persistent struggles and the potential for healing and growth.

Keywords: *adolescent lesbians, coming out, culture, religious beliefs, societal expectations*

Introduction

In today's world, where identities are as diverse as the individuals who embody them, the coming-out journeys of adolescent lesbians are powerful narratives of bravery, authenticity, and self-discovery. These journeys are often fraught with the fear of rejection, negative stereotypes, discrimination, and internalized homophobia. As society evolves, it becomes increasingly essential to acknowledge and appreciate the stories of these young individuals. This study seeks to unravel the struggles and triumphs of adolescent lesbians as they navigate the complexities of their coming-out process. By exploring these narratives, the research aims to foster empathy, challenge biases, and dismantle the stereotypes that persist in society.

Adolescence represents a critical period of self-discovery and identity formation, a time when individuals begin to understand who they are and what path they wish to follow. For many within the LGBTQ+ community, this stage is particularly challenging, as it involves the discovery of one's sexual orientation—a process often complicated by societal expectations and cultural norms. Among these challenges, the act of coming out stands as one of the most significant. In a country like the Philippines, where traditional values and cultural norms are deeply ingrained, the coming-out process is particularly difficult. As highlighted by Stahl, Love, and Terepka (2021), the familial context is crucial in disclosing one's sexual orientation. A healthy parent-child relationship is vital to the overall well-being of adolescents, yet the coming-out process is not always met with acceptance. This rejection can lead to significant mental health challenges, including internalized homophobia and perceived rejection, which are common cultural barriers for homosexual adolescents (Maniago, 2018). This study is conducted to raise awareness about the experiences of teenage lesbians and to emphasize the urgency of addressing their struggles. It also aims to provide insights for adolescent lesbians seeking guidance on how to navigate these challenges.

In the Philippines, heterosexual norms are deeply rooted in social, religious, and cultural factors. The nation's traditional practices, many of which have persisted since the Spanish colonial period, are heavily influenced by religious teachings that view heterosexuality as the normative form of romantic relationships. Homosexuality, by contrast, is often considered taboo. This cultural and societal close-mindedness creates significant barriers for LGBTQ+ individuals, making acceptance and respect difficult to achieve. According to a 2021 report by the National Sexual Violence Resource Center (NSVRC), 40% of lesbian women in the LGBTQIA+ community have experienced rape, physical violence, or stalking, and 70% have faced sexual harassment in the workplace (Heinze, 2021). These experiences contribute to a decline in mental health, often leading to mental health issues and, in extreme cases, suicide. Hate crimes against the LGBTQ+ community remain rampant, driven by societal prejudice against homosexuality. The fear of rejection and potential harm prevents many lesbians from being open about their sexuality. In today's society, which is still steeped in outdated norms, coming out can seem more harmful than beneficial for these young individuals.

Despite the Philippines' growing openness towards the LGBTQ+ community, many still face discrimination, prejudice, and stigma. Failure to conform to social norms results in discrimination on multiple levels: as women in a patriarchal society and as homosexuals in a heterosexist society. Lesbians often engage in self-policing to protect themselves and their families, as lesbianism is frequently seen as a source of shame. Common derogatory phrases like "Maghanap kayo ng tunay na lalaki" (get yourself a real man) are used to mock lesbians, reinforcing the notion that women must engage in heterosexual relationships to be considered "real" women. This non-

conformity with traditional expectations, such as marriage to the opposite sex and having children, subjects LGBTQIA+ individuals to increased discrimination. This discrimination, in turn, heightens their vulnerability to trauma, mental health issues, antisocial behavior, and human rights abuses. Some LGBTQIA+ individuals, having internalized the belief that their non-heterosexual orientation is a mental illness, may turn to addictive behaviors like drinking alcohol and smoking cigarettes as coping mechanisms (Dekdeken, 2019). The oppressive social structures and high risk of discrimination make it exceedingly difficult for lesbian teens to come out or to be open about their gender identity. As Prof. Riyan Portuguese, co-convenor of the LGBT Psychology Special Interest Group of the Psychological Association of the Philippines, notes, many LGBTQ+ youth conceal their identities and are hesitant to come out. The widespread misconception that LGBT individuals are always happy obscures the reality of their struggles. Prof. Riyan has received numerous distressing messages from young people seeking advice on how to cope with the challenges of coming out, highlighting the isolation and self-doubt that many LGBTQ+ youth experience. As Prof. Riyan eloquently summarizes, LGBT+ youth do not fail due to a lack of talent but because they feel uncomfortable, insecure, and neglected (Castañeda, 2018).

The cultural expectations of Filipino society, exemplified by figures like Barbie and Ken, have shaped our understanding of adolescence. Yet, these norms often exclude or overlook the experiences of teenage lesbians, who face significant discrimination in a judgmental environment. Filipino culture assumes that everyone will be heterosexual, creating immense pressure for those who do not conform. This research aims to shed light on the challenges faced by adolescent lesbians in the Philippines, examining them through the lens of Filipino society and culture, which is a complex web of expectations, standards, and identities. According to Ocampo, Tibudan, Marcelo, and Tus (2021), LGBTQ+ families are strong, resilient, and self-sufficient, raising their children amidst a critical society. However, lesbian teenagers face immense challenges as they confront societal discrimination alongside their families, who may also face criticism for having a lesbian child. Braga et al. (2018) have documented the negative impact on the well-being and quality of life for lesbian adolescents whose families respond violently to their coming out process, further complicating their journey.

The coming-out process is fraught with challenges due to the discrimination and stigma that persist in society and within Filipino families. In religiously conservative societies, homosexuality is often viewed as a sin, adding another layer of difficulty for young lesbians who may feel compelled to hide their true selves. The unresolved tension of coming out can lead to anxiety, mental health problems, self-harm, or even suicide. Moreover, coming out is not a straightforward or linear process; it requires courage and support. This study seeks to delve deeply into these struggles and document the stories of those who have navigated this challenging journey. The researchers utilized criteria based on the Research Guides of 2023 from Brock University Library, which emphasize purpose, credibility, reliability, timeliness, and objectivity in evaluating sources. These criteria ensure a meaningful and detailed study. Research indicates that the exclusion of LGBTQ+ individuals can lower a country's economic value. By allowing the LGBTQ+ community to exercise their human rights, a nation's economy can thrive, creating opportunities for all (Badgett et al., 2019).

Research Questions

This study's primary purpose is to uncover the stories of adolescent lesbians in their coming-out process. Specifically, this study sought to answer: What are the lived experiences of adolescent lesbians in their coming-out process?

Literature Review

The Complex Reality of Coming Out for Adolescent Lesbians in the Philippines

The amount of prejudice, discrimination, and stigma that stems from the heteronormative and religious mindset of Filipinos makes the process of coming out for adolescent lesbians challenging. Filipinos think of lesbians and other members of the LGBTQ+ community as someone lower than them. This heterosexist mindset results in the rampant and alarming amount of catcalling, rape, physical abuse, and stalking which leads the adolescent lesbians to be wary of our society. Due to these challenges, adolescent lesbians choose to repress and hide their true selves and identity, which can lead to problems like internalized homophobia, anxiety, self-harm, and even suicide.

However, recent work on the topic suggests that in the Philippines, almost three-quarters of adult Filipinos think that homosexuality should be accepted by society (Poushter & Kent, 2020). According to Dungca (2023), during the 2019 Pride March, a record-breaking 70,000 people gathered to celebrate, transforming the parade into a powerful march and festival. The Philippines is considered the second most gay-friendly country in Asia-Pacific, and the country's acceptance of the LGBTQIA+ community is evident. Furthermore, several laws and ordinances have been passed in the last two decades to protect the welfare and eliminate discrimination in the community. Senator Francis Pangilinan introduced Senate Bill 689, which prohibits discrimination based on Sexual Orientation and Gender Identity or Expression (SOGIE). Penalties were provided if a person discriminated against anyone, regardless of status or SOGIE.

The Philippine Department of Education took a step further by issuing the GenderResponsive Basic Education Policy, as emphasized by De Guia (2022) which commits to including the values of gender equity, gender sensitivity, non-discrimination, and human rights in the delivery and management of basic education. By solving these issues, it requires more than laws and ordinances- everyone who shapes the beings of these adolescents should work together to make sure that everyone has safe and inclusive places conducive to a more accepting society.

The Unique Struggles of Adolescent Lesbians: Navigating Acceptance and Identity in a Heteronormative Society

A considerable amount of research has already been done about LGBTQ+ issues in the Philippines, providing a wide spectrum of topics concerning discrimination, societal perceptions, legal rights, and such. However, little research has been done about the specific challenges that are confronted by adolescent lesbians within this broader context. While existing research has provided valuable knowledge about the coming out process of the LGBTQ+ community, it often overlooks the unique stories, experiences, journeys, triumphs, and fears of lesbian adolescents as they find their way in the process of coming out and embracing their true selves.

This is significant because it puts light on the intricate societal landscape in the Philippines, where religious and entrenched heteronormative norms pursue. While claims suggest that the Philippines is considered one of the most accepting countries concerning the LGBTQ+ community, and show that three-quarters of adult Filipinos think that homosexuality should be accepted by society (Poushter & Kent, 2020), research showed that adolescent lesbians still face stigma, prejudice, and discrimination. With that being said, it is vital to understand and investigate that despite all of these notable societal progress and implementations of legislative measures to ensure safety amongst LGBTQ+ rights, there are persisting challenges encountered by young adolescent lesbians which makes it harder for them to acknowledge and reveal their authentic self.

For the LGBTQIA+ community, the process of coming out can be quite stressful, and one's experiences may vary from another. Some people may encounter a loving and supportive environment like Rhegie Vergara. According to Castañeda in 2018, Rhegie, a 15-year-old gay man in Batangas, stated that his family and their community have known that he is gay ever since he was in kindergarten. The question remains; can all or some adolescent lesbians be as fortunate as him in finding acceptance in their sexuality? It is uncertain to determine these types of circumstances, as one's experiences may vary from one another. Braga et al. (2018) study indicated that any form of negative reaction coming from family members can harm the mental health of the LGBTQIA+ community. This claim can be supported by Green, Price-Feeny, and Dorison's (2020) study, which stated that compared to past years of reported suicide attempts, the number of attempts has decreased by over 40%. It is because all kinds of peer and adult acceptance, especially parental acceptance, lowered the odds of suicide attempts compared to those members of the LGBTQIA+ community who had little to no acceptance.

The Silent Struggles: Navigating Familial and Cultural Barriers

Nevertheless, despite numerous studies indicating that the Philippines is open to accepting the LGBTQIA+ community, it still hurts the notion of why countless members of the LGBTQ community, especially teenage lesbians, are still living in the dark and are hesitant to come out? The hesitation to come out of the closet is mainly influenced by familial contexts. As stated in Braga et al. (2018) study, the common reactions that the LGBTQIA+ community, especially adolescents, face when coming out are violence, abuse, and mistreatment, as well as being kicked out of the house. Furthermore, the need to repress homoerotic feelings can have a detrimental effect on their health and quality of life. As mentioned earlier by Stahl, Love, and Terepka (2021), coming out to one's family is one of the most difficult processes to navigate. That said, what can be the consequences that the LGBTQ+ community faces if their coming up process is not met with a positive and understanding approach? Without proper support and acceptance, an individual may suffer from mental health problems, including substance abuse, self-harm, or even worse suicide.

These disparities must be investigated to examine the autobiographical evidence of Filipino homosexual youths' coming-out experiences. Previous research has proved the collective experience of adolescents of the LGBTQ+ community as a difficult feat due to the several negative impacts it has. A study conducted based on Coming Out to Parents in Japan: A Sociocultural Analysis of Lived Experiences stated the reactions of their parents upon coming out was rather dismissive and abusive, considering the cultural factors that emphasize the heteronormative norms in Japanese homes (Tamagawa, 2018). In another research conducted about a survey of LGBTQ+ students in China, it showed that some students were comfortable with coming out. However; the majority of the youth have remained closeted. It also showed that Chinese LGBTQ+ were prone to having psychological distress, wherein about 85% of them felt depressed and around 40% had suicidal thoughts (Wei & Liu, 2019).

To integrate their identities, LGBTQ+ people must go through the process of coming out, and the results may vary greatly depending on the circumstances of the individual. Regardless of initiatives and advances toward the inclusion of homosexual people in the community, they still face an extensive amount of unfair treatment. This form of racial bias makes it difficult for Filipino adolescents to express themselves publicly with the truth about who they are, and thinking about coming out can cause worry about experiencing estrangement from loved ones and society at large.

The Complex Realities of Coming Out for Adolescent Lesbians in Filipino Society

The subject matter of this paper seeks to shed light on the realities of young lesbians' coming-out experiences. In order to prepare them for how they would interact in the culture they were born into, the researchers want to emphasize how important it is for adolescents to be aware of their gender identity and sexual orientation. Additionally, by looking at adolescent lesbians within the prism of Filipino society and culture, which is a maze of expectations, standards, and identities, researchers hope to draw attention to the difficulties that young lesbians in the Philippines experience. With that being said, if the issue of coming out as a person is not handled, it could cause them anxiety as they reveal their genuine selves and constantly worry about what is wrong with them. Inability to resolve this issue may result in mental health issues, self-harm, or, even worse, suicide. Due to this type of racism, it is challenging for Filipino teenagers to publicly express their true selves, and the idea of coming out might make them fearful of being rejected by their loved ones and

society as a whole. Therefore, this paper raises awareness about the experiences of adolescent lesbians and creates a sense of urgency in addressing their struggles. It would also serve as a means of assistance to adolescent lesbians who are looking for insight into how to overcome this situation.

Methodology

Research Design

This research utilized a descriptive qualitative research method, specifically a phenomenological approach. The phenomenological method is used to explore human phenomena at a higher level of consciousness in order to better understand life experiences. In addition, a phenomenological approach puts emphasis on gaining an in-depth understanding of phenomena gathered from the participant's perspectives and views (Qutoshi, 2018).

Participants

The researchers employed purposive sampling, selecting participants based on predetermined criteria suitable for the research objectives. Seven (7) participants were selected, aligning with the sample size recommended for a descriptive-phenomenological approach, which typically ranges from 6 to 10 participants (Morse, 1994).

Instrument

A researcher-developed semi-structured interview, which had been validated by experts in the field of Psychology, was utilized to examine the lived experiences of adolescent lesbians. This interview tool was meticulously designed and included a series of open-ended questions aimed at exploring various aspects of the participants' lives, such as their personal identification, family dynamics, interpersonal relationships, and interactions within their communities. The validation process ensured the reliability and relevance of the questions, enabling the researchers to gather comprehensive and meaningful data that accurately reflected the participants' experiences.

Procedure

The data collection process began with briefing the adolescent lesbian participants on the study's objectives, specifically aimed at uncovering their coming-out experiences. Researchers provided consent forms, ensuring participants that all information would remain confidential and that their data would be protected. Audio recording of the interviews was also proposed, subject to the participants' approval. During data collection, researchers conducted semi-structured interviews. This method allowed for the use of predetermined questions while providing flexibility for follow-up inquiries based on the participants' responses. Subsequently, the collected data were transcribed for analysis to ensure accuracy. In cases where participants did not consent to audio recording, an additional researcher accompanied the interviewer to take detailed notes. Participants were informed that they were not obligated to stay for the entire interview; however, those who chose to do so contributed significantly to the study's depth and substance.

Ethical Considerations

The research focused on adolescent lesbians coming out adhered to rigorous ethical standards to guide the study. Informed consent was obtained to ensure participants were fully aware of the study's purpose, benefits, and risks. The study accepted only participants who voluntarily chose to participate. Those who felt coerced had the option to withdraw from the study at any time. Participants' identities and personal information were kept anonymous and confidential to ensure their safety.

Ethical considerations were established to protect both participants and researchers, in compliance with the American Psychological Association's guidelines:

Respect for Autonomy: The study respected participants' autonomy by allowing them to make informed decisions regarding their involvement. An informed consent form provided details about the study's background, purpose, procedures, risks, and benefits.

Benevolence: The researchers aimed to maximize benefits while minimizing harm. Measures were implemented to protect participants from any potential harm.

Justice: The study ensured fairness by being open to all individuals willing to participate, promoting equality, and rejecting any form of discrimination.

Privacy and Confidentiality: Participants' information was secured to maintain privacy. Data collected was kept confidential and disclosed only with participants' consent.

Informed Consent: Informed consent was provided to ensure participants understood the study, gave legal authorization to participate, and were informed of the study's purpose, procedures, risks, and benefits. Participants had the right to withdraw at any stage.

Competence: The study verified that participants were physically and mentally capable of providing the required information.

Professional Integrity: The study was conducted with honesty and transparency, ensuring accurate reporting and adherence to ethical

standards.

Overall, ethical guidelines were implemented to ensure the study was conducted accurately and ethically, in accordance with the American Psychological Association's standards.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the emerging themes gathered from the participant's responses to the study's research questions by utilizing interviews. This part is composed of a table that showcases both the superordinate and subordinate themes of this study, which includes the diverse experiences of the participants concerning their coming-out processes.

Table 1. *Emerging Themes*

<i>Superordinate Themes</i>	<i>Subordinate Themes</i>
The coming-out process in various social and cultural contexts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Circumstances and emotions that disclose sexual orientation to others - Role of social and cultural background in shaping the coming-out journey - Navigating the challenges - Role of society and culture in acceptance and understanding - One's personal growth and development
Personal, familial and societal narratives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Key events or moments in life that triggered for the coming-out process - Reaction of family - Societal narratives or stereotypes encountered - Formed support systems within the LGBTQIA+ community - Changes in self-identity, well-being or social integration
Role of support systems in shaping one's coming out process	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Influence of support systems - Interactions in coming-out journey - Familial support in making the decision - Encounters with the LGBTQIA+ community resources - Interplay of support system alongside with personal resilience

Influence of various social and cultural contexts on this pivotal experience. The study identified several sub-themes: (1) circumstances and emotions that disclose sexual orientation to others. Participants described a spectrum of experiences, from moments of profound vulnerability to instances of unexpected acceptance or rejection. These narratives highlighted how personal emotions and the context of disclosure—such as familial or social settings—significantly impacted the coming-out process. The research also examined the (2) role of social and cultural background in shaping the coming-out journey, finding that cultural norms and societal expectations heavily shaped individuals' experiences. In cultures where traditional values predominated, such as in the Filipino context, participants (3) navigated the challenges, including societal stigma and familial pressure. These cultural influences were pivotal in shaping how individuals navigated their coming-out journeys and sought acceptance.

Additionally, the research explored the (4) role of society and culture in acceptance and understanding, significantly impacting individuals' personal growth and development. The study revealed that societal attitudes and cultural norms either facilitated or hindered the coming-out process. Participants who encountered supportive environments reported enhanced (5) one's personal growth and development. Conversely, those in unsupportive or hostile environments often experienced increased stress and self-doubt, affecting their overall well-being. The findings underscored the importance of societal and cultural support in fostering a positive coming-out experience and emphasized the need for continued efforts to create inclusive and accepting environments. The study provided a comprehensive understanding of how diverse social and cultural contexts influence the coming-out process and highlighted the critical role of acceptance in promoting personal development.

Personal, familial and societal narratives. (1) Key events or moments in their lives that triggered the coming-out process were meticulously documented, highlighting how pivotal incidents such as personal revelations or significant life changes prompted individuals to disclose their sexual orientation. The (2) reactions of family members were analyzed in detail, revealing a spectrum of responses from acceptance and support to resistance and denial. These familial responses played a crucial role in shaping the adolescents' experiences, influencing their emotional well-being and their subsequent decision to come out. (3) Societal narratives and stereotypes encountered by participants were also examined, illustrating the impact of prevailing prejudices and cultural norms on their coming-out journey. These societal factors often intensified the challenges faced by adolescent lesbians, reinforcing feelings of isolation and stigmatization.

The study also explored the (4) formation of support systems within the LGBTQIA+ community, which provided crucial assistance and validation for the participants. The research demonstrated how engagement with supportive peer groups and community networks facilitated coping and resilience during the coming-out process. Additionally, the study analyzed (5) changes in self-identity, well-being, and social integration following the coming-out process. The findings indicated that while some participants experienced enhanced self-acceptance and improved social integration, others faced ongoing difficulties in adjusting to their new self-identity and navigating societal expectations. The research underscored the complex interplay between personal, familial, and societal factors in

shaping the coming-out experiences of adolescent lesbians, revealing both the obstacles and the sources of support encountered throughout their journey.

Role of support systems in shaping one's coming out process. The study revealed that support systems played a pivotal role in shaping the coming-out process for adolescent lesbians. The analysis underscored that the (1) influence of support systems, including familial support and (2) interactions in coming-out journey with the LGBTQIA+ community, significantly impacted participants' experiences. (3) Familial support in making the decision emerged as a critical factor in the decision to come out, with positive familial interactions often facilitating a more affirmative coming-out experience. Conversely, the lack of family support or negative familial responses frequently exacerbated the challenges faced by participants. (4) Encounters with LGBTQIA+ community resources also provided vital assistance, offering emotional support, practical advice, and a sense of belonging that helped individuals navigate their coming-out journey. The (5) interplay between these support systems and personal resilience was evident, as participants often drew strength from both their support networks and their internal fortitude to overcome obstacles.

The study further highlighted the complex interactions between personal resilience and external support systems. Participants who reported strong support networks, including empathetic family members and active involvement with LGBTQIA+ resources, generally experienced a more positive coming-out process. In contrast, those with limited or negative support encountered greater difficulties, which often led to increased stress and uncertainty. The findings underscored the necessity of comprehensive support structures for adolescent lesbians, demonstrating that the combined influence of familial support, community resources, and personal resilience collectively shaped their coming-out experiences. This interplay of factors reinforced the importance of fostering supportive environments and resources to enhance the well-being and confidence of individuals navigating their sexual orientation in a culturally challenging context.

Conclusions

The diverse experiences of the participants in their coming-out processes reveal a nuanced interplay of familial dynamics, personal resilience, and societal expectations. Participants navigated a spectrum of responses from their closest circles, ranging from acceptance and support to conditional approval and early rejection. Over time, while the emotional scars of rejection began to heal, participants discovered new opportunities for personal growth and self-discovery. It was clear that community support played a pivotal role in empowering LGBTQIA+ individuals, providing them with a profound sense of belonging and understanding. The transformative influence of a supportive network—including partners, family, and friends—significantly shaped their coming-out journeys. This research highlights the intricate relationship between personal resilience, familial acceptance, and interactions with other LGBTQIA+ individuals, emphasizing the diversity of experiences shared by the participants.

To foster positive outcomes for lesbian adolescents navigating their coming-out processes, it is crucial to create and sustain inclusive and supportive environments. Based on the findings, it is recommended that:

Family and Community Support Programs: Develop and implement programs aimed at educating families and communities about LGBTQIA+ issues and the importance of acceptance and support. These programs should focus on creating safe spaces for open dialogues and fostering understanding to mitigate the impact of rejection.

Resilience and Self-Acceptance Initiatives: Promote initiatives that support personal resilience and self-acceptance among LGBTQIA+ adolescents. Workshops and counseling services that emphasize self-trust, self-expression, and coping strategies can aid individuals in navigating their coming-out journeys and integrating their identities.

Inclusive Policies and Practices: Advocate for and implement inclusive policies within educational and social institutions that support LGBTQIA+ individuals. This includes ensuring that policies address discrimination, provide resources for mental health support, and celebrate diversity.

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